

Experiments using a Distributed Web Crawler to Process and Index Web Archives

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Web archives are an effort to collect parts of the World Wide Web as cultural heritage and for research. Web archives are often stored using the WARC format [1] an ISO standard since 2009. The WARC format "freezes" the internet traffic between a client (a web crawler or browser) and web servers at the HTTP protocol level: content payload, HTTP headers and connection metadata (eg. the IP address) are archived but lower protocol levels (TCP/IP, TLS) are not preserved.

Web archives are used in information retrieval research since long (e.g. the ClueWeb09 dataset [2]) because they allow to run reproducible experiments on the same data independent from time and location – nothing a search engine crawler can guarantee as web pages change or even disappear over time. Also the creators of distributed web search engine crawlers have utilized web archives to test their processing pipelines. An early is Apache Nutch's ArcSegmentCreator [3] which feeds the document parser and the indexer from a web archive replacing the component fetching content from web servers. Another example is Stormcrawler [4], a software library and collection of reusable components that developers can leverage to build their own low-latency and scalable web crawlers. Stormcrawler is written mostly in Java and is provided under the Apache License. It is used by several organizations and companies for full-text indexing, data mining and web archiving.

In this talk I will present a couple of experiments run on Stormcrawler and focused around web archives. In particular:

- introduce Stormcrawler's components for creating and consuming web archives
- utilize a single architecture to process and index web pages, independent from whether the pages are fetched from the original web server or are taken from web archives
- test and benchmark the processing pipeline of a search engine crawler, including document parsers, filters and the indexing component
- usage of web archives as search engine page cache

[1] <https://iipc.github.io/warc-specifications/specifications/warc-format/warc-1.1/>

[2] <https://www.lemurproject.org/clueweb09/>

[3] <https://nutch.apache.org/apidocs/apidocs-1.16/org/apache/nutch/tools/arc/ArcSegmentCreator.html>

[4] <https://stormcrawler.net/>